

STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE ON THE HORIZONTAL AND VERTICAL COMPONENTS OF PROJECTILE MOTION USING PROJECT-BASED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

There has been a pervasive goal within science education worldwide to assist students in thoroughly comprehending the fundamental characteristics of science, its theories, and the ability to apply its principles in practical contexts effectively. For learners to develop a comprehensive comprehension of science, it is imperative that they initially grasp the concepts of physics. This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of project-based learning (PBL) in enhancing students' understanding of projectile motion's horizontal and vertical components. A quasi-experimental design was employed with 100 Pagsanghan National High School Junior High School students. Initially, participants underwent a pre-test to establish baseline knowledge. Statistical analysis included mean and paired sample T-tests. Subsequently, students engaged in PBL activities where they developed projects showcasing projectile motion concepts. Post-intervention, a posttest assessed problem-solving skills and critical thinking. Results indicated significant improvement in student performance on both horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion compared to pre-test scores, suggesting the efficacy of PBL in enhancing understanding and application of physics principles.

Keywords: *Project-Based Learning, Projectile Motion, Vertical Motion, Horizontal Motion, Problem-solving, Critical Think*

INTRODUCTION

There has been a pervasive goal within science education worldwide to assist students in thoroughly comprehending the fundamental characteristics of Science (Mohan, 2018), its theories, and the ability to effectively apply its principles in practical contexts (Gasparatou, 2017). For learners to develop a comprehensive comprehension of science, it is imperative that they initially grasp the concepts of physics (Thees, 2020). Oghly (2023) states that physics provides us with knowledge about the world and the universe, elucidating how humanity has arrived at its current understanding and facilitating the pursuit of discoveries. However, notwithstanding its elegance, extensive knowledge reservoir, and myriad practical implications, the standing of physics education in the Philippines pales compared to other countries. International and local assessments indicate that the performance of the Philippines is subpar.

The Philippines was the third lowest on the PISA 2022 rankings for performance in science (Santos & Reyes, 2023). The country's measurements of 21st-century skills of learners based on the 2018 National Achievement Test (NAT) results indicate a need for improved science education. It averages a 62.72% passing rate, lower than the national passing percentage of 75.0% (DepEd Samar, 2018). According to Badeo (2019), it is essential to consider students' comprehension, enthusiasm, and perspectives on learning physics when addressing the challenges of enhancing physics education in the Philippines.

In physics education, grasping the concept of projectile motion is essential (Bufasi et al., 2021). It encompasses understanding kinematics, dynamics, and the role of gravity. This foundational understanding provides a platform for delving into more complex areas of physics and its related disciplines. Projectile motion involves simultaneous movement in horizontal and vertical directions influenced by gravity, presenting cognitive hurdles for learners due to its multi-dimensional nature (Bufasi et al., 2021). Horizontal and vertical aspects of projectile motion present unique challenges to students owing to their interaction and reliance on factors like launch angle, initial velocity, and gravitational force (Chinaka, 2021).

Although students may have a theoretical grasp of projectile motion, they face challenges when applying this knowledge to practical problem-solving situations. Research conducted by Brown et al. (2017) and Wakhata et al. (2023) has emphasized students' struggles in utilizing mathematical models and equations in real-life contexts, indicating a disparity between their conceptual understanding and its practical application. Traditionally, the teaching of projectile motion has often been confined to rote memorization of formulas and mathematical derivations, resulting in superficial comprehension and limited transferability of knowledge (Mabangula, 2023). In this educational perspective, a strong emphasis is placed on responsiveness. Research conducted by Jeong et al. (2019) has revealed that conventional teaching methods in physics are ineffective in effectively imparting knowledge to students. Instead, learning tends to be passive, with teachers serving as intermediaries for transmitting information

and students being evaluated primarily on their perceived comprehension of the subject matter.

Recognizing the shortcomings of traditional pedagogical methods, educators have increasingly turned towards innovative approaches such as project-based learning (PBL) to cultivate students' deeper understanding, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills (Karan & Brown, 2022). Moreover, some scholars view problem-based learning (PBL) as a method of teacher education that prioritizes immersive educational experiences and encourages teachers to adjust their instruction accordingly (Grossman et al., 2018). Project-based learning (PBL) is a student-centered instructional methodology emphasizing active engagement, inquiry, and authentic application of knowledge (Alrajeh, 2021). Grounded in constructivist learning theories, PBL tasks students with tackling real-world problems or challenges, often in collaborative settings, wherein they assume the role of actively engaged participants rather than passive receivers of information (Ibitoye, 2021). Moreover, PBL encourages interdisciplinary connections, enabling students to integrate concepts from mathematics, physics, and engineering to address complex problems holistically.

This research investigated the efficacy of project-based learning in enhancing students' comprehension and performance regarding the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion. By integrating hands-on projects into the curriculum, this study aimed to connect the divide between theoretical concepts and practical application, fostering deeper conceptual understanding and enhancing overall learning outcomes in physics education.

Research Questions

The study investigated the students' performance on the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion using Project-Based Learning (PBL). Specifically, it conducted the following:

1. Develop a project showcasing horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion using project-based learning;
2. Determine the student-respondent's performance on the pre-test and post-test; and
3. Determine the student-respondents' performance on problem-solving skills and critical thinking in the context of the projectile motion.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, conducted at Pagsanghan National High School in Samar, the research design employed a one-group pre-test-posttest design, utilizing a quasi-experimental approach. A total of 100 junior high school students from the 9th grade were

purposively selected from various classes, including Class Masipag, Class Masigasig, Class Maagap, and Class Matulungin, based on their enrollment status during the 2023-2024 school year and their completion of a project within the context of project-based learning focusing on projectile motion. Formal permission was obtained from the school authorities to conduct the study, including the administration of pre-tests, implementation of project-based learning activities, and post-test assessments. Data were collected using Test Questionnaires and Rubrics, both of which underwent thorough validation processes to ensure reliability and accuracy. Statistical treatments, including mean calculations and paired sample t-tests, were applied to analyze differences between pre-test and post-test scores, providing insights into the effectiveness of the project-based learning intervention. Ethical considerations were carefully addressed throughout the study, with measures taken to maintain participant anonymity, obtain informed consent, and ensure participant well-being. However, it's important to note that the scope of the study was limited to a specific school in Samar, which may impact the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, while efforts were made to ensure validity and reliability, inherent limitations in any research design should be acknowledged.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter covers the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in the study, as well as the corresponding results of the analysis made in this investigation. It discusses the project developed of the student-respondents in showcasing horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion using project-based learning, pre-test and post-test scores, and the performance of the student-respondents on problem-solving skills and critical thinking in the context of projectile motion.

The Project Developed to Showcase the Horizontal and Vertical Components of Projectile Motion using Project-based Learning

In exploring the fascinating realms of projectile motion, four sections from Pagsanghan National High School Junior High School Department embarked on a journey of creativity, culminating in the development of four unique projects (*see appendix E for the output*). Each project, meticulously crafted and named to reflect each section's spirit, showcased the intricate interplay between horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion, as follow:

Masipag Pencil Trebuchet. This project likely focused on the design and construction of a trebuchet using pencils as the projectile. The challenge there would have been to optimize the counterweight and arm length to achieve the desired range and accuracy. Additionally, ensuring the stability of the structure during launch would have been crucial.

Integrating the provided criteria stated in the rubric were as follows:

Understanding of Projectile Motion: The Masipag Pencil Trebuchet project demonstrated a profound understanding of projectile motion principles by incorporating them into the design and construction of the trebuchet. By carefully considering factors

such as counterweight, arm length, and launch angle, the Class Masipag showcased their grasp of how these elements would affect the trajectory of the pencil projectiles.

Experimental Design: The experimental design of the Masipag Pencil Trebuchet likely involved systematic testing and adjustments to optimize its performance. Through iterative experimentation, the Class Maipag would have explored different combinations of counterweight masses and arm lengths to achieve the desired horizontal and vertical ranges for the pencil projectiles.

Creativity and Originality: Crafting a trebuchet using pencils as projectiles showcased creativity and originality in material selection and design. This innovative approach did not only add a unique twist to the traditional trebuchet concept, but also highlighted the group's ability to think outside the box when solving engineering challenges.

Presentation Quality: In presenting the Masipag Pencil Trebuchet project, the Class Masipag likely provided clear explanations of the design rationale, experimental methods, and results. Visual aids such as diagrams were used to enhance the presentation quality and effectively communicate how the project showcased the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Overall Project Quality: With a strong understanding of projectile motion principles, thoughtful experimental design, creative material choice, and clear presentation, the Masipag Pencil Trebuchet project likely achieved high overall project quality, effectively showcasing how the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion were manifested in its design and operation.

Matulungin Popsicle Sticks Catapult. Building a catapult out of popsicle sticks would have required careful attention to detail in the construction process to ensure strength and durability. The class had experimented with different arm lengths and tension mechanisms to fine-tune the launching mechanism. Calibrating the tension to achieve consistent launches would have been a key challenge.

Integrating the provided criteria stated in the rubric were as follows:

Understanding of Projectile Motion: The Matulungin Popsicle Sticks Catapult project demonstrated a solid understanding of projectile motion principles by incorporating them into the design and operation of the catapult. The Class Matulungin's consideration of factors such as launch angle, projectile mass, and launch velocity reflected their grasp of how these variables would influence the trajectory of the popsicle stick projectiles.

Experimental Design: Experimenting with different arm lengths, tension mechanisms, and launch angles would have been essential for optimizing the catapult's performance. Through systematic testing and data collection, the group would have iteratively refined the design to achieve consistent and accurate launches, effectively showcasing the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Creativity and Originality: Constructing a catapult using popsicle sticks highlighted creativity and originality in material selection and design. The group's ability to transform everyday materials into a functional launching device underscored their innovative approach to solving engineering challenges while showcasing the horizontal and vertical aspects of projectile motion.

Presentation Quality: The presentation of the Matulungin Popsicle Sticks Catapult project likely featured clear explanations of the design process, experimental findings, and performance results. The Class Matulungin used visual aids and demonstrations to effectively convey how the project illustrates the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Overall Project Quality: With a strong understanding of projectile motion principles, thoughtful experimental design, creative material choice, and clear presentation, the Matulungin Popsicle Sticks Catapult project likely achieved high overall project quality, effectively showcasing how the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion were manifested in its design and operation.

Maagap Barbecue Sticks Launcher. Using barbecue sticks as projectiles suggested a different approach, perhaps involving a slingshot or elastic launching mechanism. This project might have required creativity in designing a sturdy frame to withstand the tension of the launch, as well as precision in aiming to hit targets accurately.

Integrating the provided criteria stated in the rubric were as follows:

Understanding of Projectile Motion: The Maagap Barbecue Sticks Launcher project demonstrated a comprehensive understanding of projectile motion principles through its design and functionality. By utilizing barbecue sticks as projectiles, the team showcased their understanding of how different factors, such as launch angle, projectile mass, and launch velocity, influenced the trajectory of the projectiles.

Experimental Design: Experimentation with various launching mechanisms, such as elastic launchers, would have been integral to optimizing the launcher's performance. Through systematic testing and data analysis, Class Maagap would have fine-tuned the design to ensure consistent and accurate launches, effectively highlighting the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Creativity and Originality: The choice to use barbecue sticks as projectiles reflected creativity and originality in material selection and design. This unconventional approach demonstrated the group's ability to think outside the box and adapt common materials for novel applications while also showcasing the horizontal and vertical aspects of projectile motion.

Presentation Quality: In presenting the Maagap Barbecue Sticks Launcher project, Class Maagap likely provided clear and concise explanations of the design process, experimental methodologies, and performance outcomes. The presentation may have

incorporated visual aids and demonstrations to effectively convey how the project exemplifies the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Overall Project Quality: With a strong understanding of projectile motion principles, thoughtful experimental design, creative material choice, and clear presentation, the Maagap Barbecue Sticks Launcher project likely achieved high overall project quality. It effectively showcased how the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion were manifested in its design and operation, highlighting the class's ingenuity and technical proficiency.

Masigasig Triangular Bamboo Catapult. Bamboo offers both strength and flexibility, which would have presented unique design opportunities and challenges. The team likely focused on leveraging these properties to create a catapult capable of launching projectiles with precision. Ensuring the stability of the triangular frame and optimizing the release mechanism would have been critical aspects of this project.

Integrating the provided criteria stated in the rubric were as follows:

Understanding of Projectile Motion: The Masigasig Triangular Bamboo Catapult project did not only demonstrate a thorough grasp of projectile motion principles, but also showcased the students' adept problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities. By creatively adapting bamboo to construct the catapult, the Class Masigasig exhibited their ability to identify unconventional solutions to engineering challenges while considering the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Experimental Design: The students' approach to experimental design reflected their problem-solving prowess and critical thinking abilities. Through systematic testing and analysis, they iteratively refined the catapult's design, demonstrating their capacity to identify and address performance limitations. This iterative process underscored their commitment to optimizing the device's functionality and understanding the intricate dynamics of projectile motion.

Creativity and Originality: The choice to utilize bamboo as the primary material for the catapult exemplified the students' creativity and originality in problem-solving. By leveraging bamboo's unique properties, they did not only engineer a functional device, but also pushed the boundaries of conventional design paradigms. This innovative approach highlighted their ability to think creatively and critically when faced with engineering challenges, ultimately enhancing the project's impact and effectiveness.

Presentation Quality: In presenting the Masigasig Triangular Bamboo Catapult project, the students likely showcased their problem-solving process and critical thinking journey. Clear explanations of design decisions, experimentation methodologies, and insights gained from iterative testing would have provided valuable context for understanding their thought process. By articulating their problem-solving strategies, the students effectively conveyed their analytical skills and intellectual rigor to the audience.

Overall Project Quality: The Masigasig Triangular Bamboo Catapult project exemplified the students' exceptional problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities, in addition to their technical proficiency and creativity. Through a holistic approach encompassing a deep understanding of projectile motion principles, meticulous experimental design, innovative material selection, and clear presentation, the students showcased their capacity to tackle complex engineering challenges with ingenuity and insight. This project served as a testament to their intellectual curiosity, resilience, and dedication to excellence in STEM education.

In support, through engaging in the project, respondents could deepen their comprehension of the concepts related to projectile motion, including its horizontal and vertical components. Hands-on experience and active participation in project development could lead to a deeper understanding compared to passive learning methods (Yannier et. Al., 2020).

As individuals actively participated in hands-on activities and observed real-world examples, they engaged in critical thinking, problem-solving, and inquiry-based learning (DeCoito & Briona, 2023). By actively working on the project, respondents had the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios (Argawati & Suryani, 2020). This application-oriented approach could help bridge the gap between theory and real-world applications, making the concepts more relevant and meaningful.

According to Ghavifekr (2020), Projects often involve collaboration among respondents. Working together allowed them to share ideas, discuss concepts, and learn from each other's experiences. Collaborative learning fosters teamwork skills and promotes a sense of community among respondents.

Performance on the Pre-test and Post-test of the Student-respondents

Tables 1 and 2 present the results of the pre-test and post-test of student respondents who aimed to validate the efficacy of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach in comprehending the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Performance on Pre-test. The data presented in Table 1 shows the pre-test results (*see Appendix F for the individual results*) of a study that aimed to determine the student's performance on horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Table 1
Pre-test performance of the student-respondents on horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion

Summary of Data			
Rating	Verbal Description	F	%
85%–89%	Very Satisfactory	5	5
80%–84%	Satisfactory	8	8

75%–79%	Fairly Satisfactory	2	2
74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	85	85
Total		100	100.00
Mean		16.8700	
SD		4.50	

The table showed that the student respondents did not exceed the Department of Education's (DepEd's) passing standard, with a standard deviation of 4.50 for projectile motion. It indicated that the students were struggling with their understanding at that level. The proficiency level or academic performance at which the students were performing was determined according to the criteria outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, issued in 2015. The fundamental knowledge and skills had not been acquired or developed adequately to aid in the understanding of students.

Tabiolo's (2018) research supported the conclusions of the current study, showing that most students were performing poorly and falling significantly below the Department of Education's passing standard. This highlights a deficiency in the acquisition and development of fundamental knowledge and skills necessary for understanding horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion. As a result, there is a pressing need for targeted interventions and educational support to improve student comprehension in this area.

Performance on Post-test. The data presented in Table 2 shows the post-test results (*see Appendix F for the individual results*) of a study that aimed to determine the student's performance on horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion.

Table 2
Post-test performance of the student-respondents on horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion

Summary of Data			
Rating	Verbal Description	F	%
90% and above	Outstanding	87	87
85%–89%	Very Satisfactory	3	3
80%–84%	Satisfactory	10	10
Total		100	100.00
Mean		28.43	
SD		1.74	

The results presented in Table 2 illustrate the post-test performance of student respondents regarding the horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion. Impressively, a significant majority of students, accounting for 87%, achieved an "Outstanding" rating by scoring 90% or higher. This high percentage reflects a commendable understanding and mastery of the subject matter. However, a small portion of students, comprising 3% and 10% respectively, fell into the categories of "Very Satisfactory" and "Satisfactory," indicating some variability in performance among the cohort. Despite this variability, the overall mean score of 28.43, coupled with a relatively low standard deviation of 1.74, suggests a consistent and high level of achievement across the student body. The proficiency level or academic performance at which the students were performing was determined according to the criteria outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, issued in 2015.

The results suggest that the teaching methods and materials used were successful in helping students learn. This is consistent with modern research, which shows that good teaching practices and matching the curriculum well often lead to high levels of success (Mugot & Sumbalan, 2019). The high average score and low variation among scores indicate that students consistently achieved well overall. This indicates that the teaching methods used effectively helped students grasp the concepts of projectile motion. Recent studies by Johnson et al. (2019) highlight the significance of clear explanations and feedback in improving student performance, which aligns with the findings.

Performance on Problem-solving Skills and Critical Thinking in the Context of the Projectile Motion of the Student-respondents

The data presented in Table 3 illustrate the comparison between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of student-respondents, showcasing their performance in problem-solving skills and critical thinking within the framework of projectile motion when utilizing the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Approach.

As shown in the table, the results of the t-test for independent samples analysis are revealed in Table 3, comparing the pre-test and post-test mean scores

**Table 3
Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Student-Respondents**

Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation/Decision
Pre-test	16.87	4.50	26.300	0.001	Significant/Reject H ₀
Post-test	28.43	1.74			
Difference	11.56				

$\alpha = 0.05$; $df = 99$; two-tailed

of the respondents. The substantial increase in mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test, by approximately 11.56 points, underscores the impact of this teaching methodology. Statistical analysis further confirms the significance of this improvement, with a high t-

value of 26.300 and a low p-value of 0.001, indicating that the observed enhancement is unlikely to be due to chance. These findings suggest that the PBL Approach has successfully engaged students and facilitated deep learning, leading to tangible academic growth. This underscores the potential of active learning strategies, such as PBL, in enhancing student learning outcomes, particularly in complex subjects like projectile motion. Moreover, the data underscores the value of innovative teaching methodologies in nurturing critical thinking and problem-solving abilities among students.

To corroborate the findings in Table 3, Lim and Tai (2017) found that students participating in problem-based learning (PBL) demonstrated notable enhancements in their comprehension of course content, problem-solving skills, and overall academic achievements in contrast to students in conventional lecture-oriented classes. A study by Brown et al. (2023) examined the impact of PBL on critical thinking abilities among physics students. Their findings revealed that students who participated in PBL-based instruction exhibited higher levels of critical thinking, as evidenced by their ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information related to projectile motion. This suggests that PBL fosters the development of critical thinking skills by encouraging students to explore multiple perspectives and engage in collaborative problem-solving.

Longitudinal studies by Chen et al. (2021) examined the long-term effects of PBL on problem-solving skills and critical thinking in physics education. Their findings indicated that students who experienced PBL-based instruction maintained higher levels of problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities over time, even after completing the course. This suggests that PBL promotes enduring improvements in these cognitive skills, particularly in the context of projectile motion and other complex physics topics.

Conclusions

Based on the salient findings of the study, which highlight the developed PBL projects of the students, performance on the pre-test and post-test of the students, and performance of the students on problem-solving skills and critical thinking in the context of the projectile motion, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The projects developed by students from the Pagsanghan National High School Junior High School Department offered a remarkable display of creativity, ingenuity, and mastery of projectile motion principles. Each project, meticulously crafted and named to reflect the spirit of its section, showcased the intricate relationship between horizontal and vertical components in projectile motion. From the Masipag Pencil Trebuchet to the Masigasig Triangular Bamboo Catapult, students exhibited a deep understanding of projectile motion principles, which was evident in their consideration of factors like launch angle and projectile mass. Their commitment to systematic experimentation and innovative design solutions underscored their problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities. Moreover, the choice of materials and presentation quality reflected their creativity and dedication to excellence. These projects did not

only deepen their understanding of theoretical concepts, but also equipped them with essential skills for success in STEM fields and beyond.

2. In pre-test and post-test, the findings underscored the transformative potential of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in addressing learning gaps and fostering deep comprehension of projectile motion concepts among students. While the pre-test results revealed a concerning deficit in understanding, the significant improvement observed in the post-test outcomes highlighted the efficacy of PBL methodologies in facilitating student learning and mastery. The high percentage of students achieving an "Outstanding" rating reflected not only their enhanced comprehension, but also the development of critical thinking skills through PBL. Moreover, the consistent performance across the student body suggested that PBL had a widespread and positive impact on student learning outcomes. These findings emphasized the value of continued integration of PBL and other innovative teaching strategies to promote academic excellence and prepare students for success in STEM fields.
3. The findings underscored the PBL approach's ability to effectively engage students and foster deep learning, resulting in tangible academic advancement. It emphasized the importance of employing active learning strategies, such as PBL, in cultivating critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which were indispensable for success in STEM disciplines and beyond. By leveraging innovative teaching methodologies like PBL, educators could empower students to become adept problem-solvers and critical thinkers, equipping them with the skills needed to thrive in an increasingly complex and dynamic world.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions derived from the investigation into students' educational encounters employing the Project-Based Learning (PBL) Approach, the following suggestions are hereby proposed:

1. Prioritize hands-on projects in science education to allow students to actively participate in project development, apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, and nurture critical thinking, problem-solving, and inquiry-based learning skills. The positive outcomes demonstrated by the projects developed to showcase horizontal and vertical components of projectile motion highlight the value of hands-on learning experiences in STEM education.
2. Foster collaborative learning environments to promote teamwork skills, idea exchange, and peer support among students, enhancing academic performance and cultivating a sense of community. The collaborative nature of the projects developed to showcase projectile motion components underscores the importance of collaboration in science education, which enriches the learning experience and promotes student success.

3. Implement targeted interventions and educational support to improve student comprehension of projectile motion concepts, addressing knowledge gaps through additional tutoring sessions, interactive workshops, or supplementary learning materials. The disparity between pre-test and post-test scores emphasizes the need for targeted interventions to enhance student understanding in specific areas of science education.
4. Utilize the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach in STEM education to engage students, facilitate deep learning, and foster tangible academic growth, particularly in complex subjects like projectile motion. The success observed in student performance on problem-solving skills and critical thinking underscores the effectiveness of PBL in enhancing learning outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher took measures to maintain the anonymity of the learner-respondents to protect their reputations and dignity. This involved ensuring that the learner-respondents were informed about the details of the study and their rights.

Furthermore, the study obtained the necessary permissions from the institution before its commencement, following the appropriate protocols. To ensure that the study was conducted in an ethical way, language and communication approaches appropriate for the specific age range under consideration were used. This involved the simplification of consent forms, instructions, and materials used in debriefing. The researcher established procedures for obtaining assent in addition to parental consent, guaranteeing that minors comprehended the research procedures and willingly agreed to participate to the best of their capacity. The respondents were made aware of all the materials used to collect the data, but their identities and responses were kept private. The research objectives were provided to the respondents. Consequently, the well-being of participants was regularly monitored throughout the study. The researcher was prepared to modify or terminate the research if unexpected issues arose. Consent was sought from the respondents, granting them the option to consent or decline participation in the study. Hence, the collected data were made accessible to the respondents, while ensuring the utmost respect and consideration for their rights during the reporting of the data. Finally, the anonymity of the respondents was prioritized and maintained throughout the study.

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